

Viscosity of Solutions of Potassium Chloride, Sodium Chloride, Potassium Bromide and Sodium Bromide in Dioxane-Water Mixtures at 30° and 40° and the Activation Energies and Entropies of Viscous Flow

B. DAS, K. SINGH & P. K. DAS

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3

Received 13 November 1971

The viscosity of Potassium chloride, Sodium chloride, Potassium bromide and Sodium bromide in 10, 20 and 30% of dioxane-water mixtures have been reported at 30° and 40°. The energies and entropies of activation for viscous flow at 35° have been calculated for such solutions.

The viscosity of solutions of Potassium chloride, Sodium chloride, Potassium bromide and Sodium bromide at 35° has been reported earlier^{1,2,3}. The investigation was undertaken not only to test the applicability of the Jones-Dole equation in these solvents and temperatures but also to calculate the activation energy and entropy of activation for viscous flow of these solutions by interpreting the influence of strong electrolytes upon the viscosity of a solvent as a rate process.

EXPERIMENTAL

The salts of E. Merck "Extra pure" quality and B.D.H. Analar quality were recrystallised from triple distilled water, dried and kept in vacuum. Purification of dioxane and other precautions taken for preparing solutions are reported previously. The concentration ranges studied are from 0.001 to 0.1 molar. The solutions investigated are at round about concentrations 0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.015, 0.02, 0.025, 0.05, 0.06, 0.08, 0.09 and 0.1 molar.

TABLE 1(A)

*Comparison of observed and calculated values of η/η_0 at two concentrations in 10%
solvent composition*

Temperature	30°			40°		
	Electrolyte	Conc.	η/η_0 Obs.	η/η_0 Calcd.	Conc.	η/η_0 Obs.
KCl	0.0151	1.0011	1.0012	0.0104	1.0009	1.0009
	0.0925	1.0034	1.0036	0.0930	1.0049	1.0048
NaCl	0.0125	1.0027	1.0029	0.0147	1.0028	1.0029
	0.0932	1.0170	1.0170	0.0931	1.0150	1.0149
KBr	0.0145	1.0011	1.0012	0.0120	1.0012	1.0012
	0.0921	1.0046	1.0045	0.0911	1.0058	1.0059
NaBr	0.0144	1.0025	1.0024	0.0155	1.0021	1.0023
	0.0912	1.0124	1.0125	0.0903	1.0104	1.0106

TABLE 1(B)

Comparison of observed and calculated values of η/η_0 at two concentrations in 20% solvent composition

Temperature		30°		40°		
Electrolyte	Conc.	η/η_0 Obs.	η/η_0 Calcd.	Conc.	η/η_0 Obs.	η/η_0 Calcd.
KCl	0.0424	1.0028	1.0028	0.0108	1.0011	1.0011
	0.0930	1.0053	1.0052	0.0915	1.0063	1.0064
NaCl	0.0142	1.0033	1.0034	1.0121	1.0025	1.0025
	0.0953	1.0191	1.0189	0.0946	1.0161	1.0162
KBr	0.0147	1.0014	1.0014	0.0125	1.0014	1.0015
	0.0930	1.0066	1.0065	0.0925	1.0079	1.0080
NaBr	0.0113	1.0022	1.0023	0.0203	1.0032	1.0031
	0.0930	1.0142	1.0141	0.0925	1.0116	1.0115

TABLE 1(C)

Comparison of observed and calculated values of η/η_0 at two concentrations in 30% solvent composition

Temperature		30°		40°		
Electrolyte	Conc.	η/η_0 Obs.	η/η_0 Calcd.	Conc.	η/η_0 Obs.	η/η_0 Calcd.
KCl	0.0145	1.0018	1.0018	0.0221	1.0028	1.0029
	0.0591	1.0050	1.0052	0.0425	1.0047	1.0048
NaCl	0.0160	1.0053	1.0052	0.0182	1.0051	1.0052
	0.0245	1.0074	1.0075	0.0381	1.0098	1.0098
KBr	0.0182	1.0023	1.0023	0.0160	1.0021	1.0022
	0.0531	1.0051	0.0052	0.0534	1.0058	1.0057
NaBr	0.0174	1.0046	1.0047	0.0182	1.0038	1.0039
	0.0464	1.0107	1.0109	0.0464	1.0087	1.0088

TABLE 2(A)

Values of A and B at 10% dioxane by weight (solvent composition)

Temperature		30°		40°		
Electrolyte	A Obs.	A Calcd.	B	A Obs.	A Calcd.	B
KCl	0.0064	0.0063	0.018	0.0056	0.0057	0.033
NaCl	0.0067	0.0069	0.160	0.0061	0.0062	0.140
KBr	0.0056	0.0058	0.030	0.0054	0.0056	0.046
NaBr	0.0057	0.0058	0.118	0.0059	0.0060	0.097

TABLE 2(B)

Values of A and B at 20% dioxane by weight (solvent composition)

Temperature	30°			40°		
Electrolyte	A Obs.	A Calcd.	B	A Obs.	A Calcd.	B
KCl	0.0067	0.0068	0.034	0.0059	0.0061	0.050
NaCl	0.0072	0.0073	0.175	0.0064	0.0064	0.150
KBr	0.0061	0.0062	0.049	0.0057	0.0058	0.067
NaBr	0.0065	0.0066	0.130	0.0062	0.0061	0.104

TABLE 2(C)

Values of A, B and x at 30% dioxane by weight (solvent composition)

Temperature	30°			40°		
Electrolyte	A Calcd.	B	x	A Calcd.	B	x
KCl	0.0075	0.044	0.93	0.0070	0.061	0.92
NaCl	0.0091	0.230	0.98	0.0089	0.200	0.98
KBr	0.0078	0.059	0.98	0.0052	0.079	0.98
NaBr	0.0086	0.186	0.99	0.0059	0.152	0.98

DISCUSSION

The experimental data of η/η_0 as well as the calculated values with the help of Jones-Dole equation and the modified Jones-Dole equation¹ for the electrolytes in the three solvents are recorded in Table 1 (A,B,C). The values of 'A', 'B' and 'x' found in the usual manner are given in Table 2 (A,B,C).

The experimental data when analysed in the light of Jones-Dole equation indicates validity of this equation in 10 and 20% dioxane-water mixtures, but in 30% dioxane-water mixture the modified equation is obeyed. From the Table 2 (C) it is evident that the value of 'x' is roughly independent of temperature and except in the case of Potassium chloride it has roughly the same value. The values of 'B' steadily increases, as the dioxane content in the solvent increases. It can also be generalised that the values of 'B' changes in the order NaCl > NaBr > KBr > KCl.

The difference between the B values of (a) KCl and NaCl and (b) KBr and NaBr, in other words the difference between B values of K⁺ and Na⁺, when combined with different anions is not the same. Hence 'B' is neither partitionable nor additive.

The interpretation of viscous flow for electrolytic solutions in water according to the theory of absolute reaction rates has been done by Nightingale⁴ and he has calculated the activation energy 'ΔE' (which does not differ appreciably from activation enthalpy), free energy of activation 'ΔF' and the entropy of activation 'ΔS' for water and a number of

electrolytic solutions. Proceeding in the similar lines the authors have calculated the energy of activation, the free energy of activation and entropy of activation for KCl, NaCl, KBr and NaBr making use of the earlier data^{1,2,3} for 10, 20 and 30% solvent composition. The results are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Solvent composition	10%			20%			30%		
	ΔE in K.cal. ± 0.03	ΔF in K.cal.	ΔS in E.U.	ΔE in K.cal. ± 0.03	ΔF in K.cal.	ΔS in E.U.	ΔE in K.cal. ± 0.03	ΔF in K.cal.	ΔS in E.U.
Solvent	4.084	2.290	5.82	4.158	2.491	5.41	4.622	2.580	6.63
KCl	3.807	2.303	4.88	3.868	2.515	4.39	4.013	2.611	4.55
NaCl	4.429	2.344	6.77	4.581	2.556	6.57	5.107	2.674	7.90
KBr	3.792	2.311	4.81	3.837	2.522	4.27	4.267	2.617	5.36
NaBr	4.439	2.357	6.76	4.594	2.563	6.59	5.166	2.676	8.10

It is observed that the energy and entropy of activation for viscous flow in case of Potassium chloride and Potassium bromide is less than that of the solvent. In case of the latter salt the decrease is larger. For the cases of Sodium chloride and Sodium bromide these quantities are higher than those of the solvent. The values are almost constant. The abnormally large energies and entropies of activation are attributed to the excess of energy necessary to break the hydrogen bonds in solutions. In the case of Potassium chloride and Potassium bromide solutions in all solvent compositions indicate that the solvent structure is broken by the presence of these electrolytes, but for Sodium chloride and Sodium bromide the ΔE and ΔS values are higher than those of the solvent. It clearly indicates that due to the presence of Na^+ the solvent structure is stabilised or in other words the Na^+ not only associates the solvent molecule in the co-sphere and stabilises the solvent structure but also predominates over the structure breaking properties of its partner.

REFERENCES

1. R. C. Acharya, P. K. Das and D. Patnaik, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 56.
2. P. K. Das, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 613.
3. P. K. Das, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 341.
4. E. R. Nightingale, Jr. and R. F. Benck, *J. Physical Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 1777.